

A Pedagogical Perspective on the Use of the Inverse Lorentz Factor in Teaching Special Relativity

Stefan Treysse

treysse@campus.tu-berlin.de

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Abstract

Most textbooks on the theory of special relativity at some point introduce the Lorentz factor γ . In this paper, we argue that γ has little pedagogical merit. On the contrary, its algebraic structure obscures the quantitative relationship between relative speed and relativistic effects. We show that the inverse of the Lorentz factor, γ^{-1} , is simpler, carries more explanatory power, and allows students, especially at the introductory level, to grasp how relativistic effects depend on relative speed.

In support of the argument, we introduce methods aimed at students with varying mathematical aptitudes to explore the relation between relative speed and relativistic effects using a marked ruler and a compass. These methods are based on Jakob Steiner's power of a point theorem.

To support this perspective, an appendix provides a set of worked problems illustrating these methods, as well as a survey of textbook treatments of the Lorentz factor.

Introduction

Special relativity is a cornerstone of modern physics, yet it is often perceived as one of the more challenging topics for students to grasp, especially at the introductory level [KC22]. Most attention is given to the conceptual difficulties students face as they are introduced to the theory. Issues students face with the mathematical framework are usually not addressed. As an original approach, this paper will show, that the mathematical formulation has the potential to improve the didactics of special relativity without sacrificing any of the mathematical rigor. Central to the mathematical framework of special relativity is the Lorentz transformation.

As part of the Lorentz transformation, most authors introduce what is often called the Lorentz factor, denoted as γ . The factor γ is defined as:

$$\gamma \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (1)$$

A key reason γ is widely used is that it streamlines the notation of the Lorentz transformation. It is also applied in formulas for time dilation and length contraction. As a conceptual tool, it is presented as a quantity that expresses the magnitude of relativistic effects. However, its complexity can create a significant barrier to understanding for students who encounter the theory for the first time. The non-linear dependence of γ on velocity v makes it difficult to build physical intuition, particularly as v approaches the speed of light c .

This article argues that the inverse of the Lorentz factor

$$\gamma^{-1} = \frac{1}{\gamma} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \quad (2)$$

offers a more intuitive and pedagogically effective approach to introducing special relativity. This inverse factor is algebraically simpler and has a sim-

pler relationship to velocity. It also provides students with a geometric method to visualize and explore relativistic effects using a compass and a ruler.

By re-framing the standard equations of special relativity in terms of γ^{-1} , students may find it easier to connect mathematical formalism with physical phenomena. Linking equations directly to geometric reasoning makes abstract concepts tangible.

This approach emphasizes geometric interpretation. Its focus not only aids in understanding but also provides a straightforward geometric method for analysis.

Besides being more straightforward, the inverse Lorentz factor reveals a geometric identity that is otherwise hidden beneath the algebraic structure of γ . The identity is found by squaring both sides of the equation and adding v^2/c^2 :

$$\frac{1}{\gamma} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \Rightarrow \left(\frac{1}{\gamma}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

This identity re-frames the relation between relative speed and relativistic effects as a trade-off rather than some external effect that somehow affects moving objects.

This paper is organized as follows: We begin by examining how textbooks introduce and utilize the Lorentz factor γ . Next, we analyze its algebraic structure and the properties of its inverse. We then explore γ as a function of relative velocity and examine its graphical representations. This leads to a geometric interpretation of γ^{-1} , which provides deeper insight into relativistic effects. Finally, we present ruler-and-compass techniques for solving simple kinematic problems.

The first appendix includes a set of worked problems illustrating the geometric methods. The second appendix presents the survey of textbooks in more detail. The last appendix includes an alternative algebraic analysis of the identity mentioned above.

1 Notation and Definitions

In this work, all velocities v are considered as fractions of the speed of light c . For clarity, we define:

$$\beta \equiv \frac{v}{c} \tag{4}$$

We introduce ϵ as the symbol for the reciprocal of γ :

$$\epsilon \equiv \sqrt{1 - \beta^2} \tag{5}$$

Event coordinates are expressed as four-tuples, i.e., (t, x, y, z) or (x_0, x_1, x_2, x_3) . This notation will also be used when events are shown as points in a diagram with only two or three axes.

2 The Lorentz Factor in Textbooks

A survey of textbooks on special relativity shows that while the Lorentz factor γ is widely introduced, its pedagogical role appears to be quite limited. Most books include γ as a standard element of the Lorentz transformation, but they rarely justify its use beyond mathematical convenience. Instead of exploring its conceptual meaning or its implications for understanding relativistic effects, textbooks primarily treat γ as a computational tool.

Only one book in the survey, [Res68], explicitly discusses the function $\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$, but even there, its significance as a fundamental quantity remains unexamined. In all other cases, $\epsilon = \gamma^{-1}$ is either omitted entirely or introduced only as a stepping stone to γ . This suggests that textbooks prioritize maintaining conventional notation over exploring alternative formulations that could enhance conceptual clarity.

The absence of discussions on ϵ and the minimal didactic treatment of γ underscore the originality of the approach presented in this paper. By shifting the focus to ϵ and its geometric interpretation, we provide an alternative framework that is both mathematically simpler and pedagogically richer. A

detailed analysis of the surveyed textbooks is provided in Appendix B.

3 The arithmetic and algebraic structure of the Lorentz factor

In this section, we show that the arithmetic and algebraic structure of γ is unnecessarily complicated. Physicists experienced in SR might wonder why students find the formula for γ intimidating or confusing. Their intuition for SR allows them to use γ without reconsidering its details and inner workings each time.

Instead of functioning as a complex algebraic element within a larger expression, it is merely an arithmetic instruction: γ is calculated and then the value is used for further calculations. At first glance, students may assume that γ 's structure is an algebraic necessity reflecting a fundamental relationship between speed and relativistic effects. However, this structure is not essential, as the division by ϵ can be performed explicitly where needed, rather than being built into γ .

The following algebraic analysis will reveal that γ is more complicated than necessary and that what is essential hides deeper geometric relations.

The explicit expression of γ consists of two main algebraic elements: the fraction and the square root.

The fraction has 1 in the numerator and the root term i.e. ϵ in the denominator:

$$\frac{1}{(\dots)} \tag{6}$$

In the root term, there is a 1 minus something squared under the root sign

$$\sqrt{1 - (\dots)^2} \tag{7}$$

We first examine (6): Since 1 is the multiplicative identity, it follows that

$$\frac{1}{(\dots)} \cdot a \Rightarrow a : (\dots) \quad (8)$$

and

$$b : \frac{1}{(\dots)} \Rightarrow b \cdot (\dots) \quad (9)$$

This confirms that the expression in the denominator ϵ determines the magnitude of relativistic effects. However, it is not its position in the denominator that causes or quantifies these effects. The position of ϵ in the denominator is merely an arithmetic instruction that is "hidden" in the formulation of γ .

Consequently, it may seem like an aesthetic choice whether coordinates, times, or lengths are multiplied and divided by γ or by ϵ . But why this is not the case will be explored in section 4.

Algebraically, there is no reason to prefer γ over ϵ . On the contrary, the explicit form of ϵ is an expression that cannot be simplified; γ on the other hand is simply its inverse ($1/\epsilon$). Hence, ϵ should be preferred as the simpler and more natural expression.

Arithmetically, some students might prefer working with numbers greater than one rather than those smaller than one. However, since such calculations are rarely performed manually today, this argument carries little weight.

Now that we have dismantled the fraction, we turn to (7) respectively to the equation for ϵ and what follows from this equation:

$$\epsilon = \sqrt{1 - \beta^2} \Rightarrow 1 = \beta^2 + \epsilon^2 \quad (10)$$

This geometric identity, which resembles the formula for the unit circle, is a strong indication that ϵ is the fundamental quantity and γ only its inverse.

And lastly, we examine the term under the square root: The term $1 - \beta^2$ appears simple but reveals little at first glance. Some students might wonder why it is meaningful to square a velocity and subtract that square from 1.

However, students who take a second look might recall that whenever an obvious square (e.g., β^2) is subtracted from a number (e.g., 1), it is worth checking whether that number is also a square.

In the case of $1 - \beta^2$, where $\beta = \frac{v}{c}$, it is useful to rewrite it as:

$$\left(\frac{c}{c} + \frac{v}{c}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{c}{c} - \frac{v}{c}\right) = (1 + \beta) \cdot (1 - \beta) = 1 - \beta^2 \quad (11)$$

Writing $\epsilon = \sqrt{(1 + \beta) \cdot (1 - \beta)}$ reveals that ϵ is the geometric mean of $(1 + \beta)$ and $(1 - \beta)$.

So, with little effort, we have established three points:

1. Placing ϵ in the denominator of γ is an arithmetic instruction rather than the expression of a fundamental algebraic relation.
2. The sum of the squares of β and ϵ gives an identity analogous to the unit circle, i.e., $1 = \beta^2 + \epsilon^2$.
3. ϵ can be interpreted as the geometric mean between $(1 + \beta)$ and $(1 - \beta)$.

The relevance of the first point will be elaborated on in the next section. The second point will be relevant in section 5. The third point is also more than a mathematical curiosity; it represents a meaningful geometric relation, as we will show in section 6.

4 The Lorentz factor as a function of speed

As mentioned above, γ can be seen as a function $\gamma(\beta)$ that somehow expresses the magnitude of relativistic effects.

While most textbooks define this function only for $\beta \in [0, 1]$, we will consider it over the full range $\beta \in [-1, 1]$ to reflect its symmetry under direction reversal.

Regardless of the chosen domain, the function $\gamma(\beta)$ has some peculiar features:

- When the relative speed $\beta = 0$, there are zero relativistic effects, but the value of γ is 1.
- As β approaches c , the value of γ approaches $+\infty$, increasing ever more rapidly for ever smaller increments in β .
- For $\beta = 1$, γ is not defined.
- So while the domain of $\gamma(\beta)$ is $] - 1, 1[$, its codomain is $[1, +\infty[$.
- Beyond the question of what it means for some effect to be infinitely large, it is clear that this divergence toward infinity is artificially created by placing $\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$ in the denominator under a fixed numerator.

While mathematically sound, this function's peculiarities make it harder to grasp its relation to physical effects.

In contrast, $\epsilon(\beta)$ is more straightforward and has a more direct interpretation:

- At $\beta = 0$, we have $\epsilon = 1$; at $\beta = 1$, we have $\epsilon = 0$.
- Its domain is $[0, 1]$ and its co-domain is also $[0, 1]$.
- ϵ directly relates an object's proper quantities—its own time intervals and lengths—to the coordinate quantities measured in an inertial frame in which the object is moving.

If the object is stationary (i.e., $\beta = 0$), then $\epsilon = 1$; consequently, its proper time and proper length align with the coordinates of the reference frame. However, when the object moves, its measured length and elapsed time change: A moving object's length is measured as shorter in the stationary frame than its proper length, and its proper time elapses slowly compared to the coordinate time.

The faster the object moves relative to the reference frame, the shorter its measured length, and the slower its proper time elapses compared to the

coordinate time. The factor governing length contraction and time dilation is ϵ , appearing in the standard relations:

$$L = \epsilon \cdot L_0, \quad \Delta\tau = \epsilon \cdot \Delta t. \quad (12)$$

Although both functions $\gamma(\beta)$ and $\epsilon(\beta)$ describe relativistic effects, they convey different narratives:

1. γ tells a story of relativistic effects that are first negligible before increasing without bound.
2. ϵ tells a story of a trade-off between relative movement on one side and measured length and elapsed time on the other.

While the first highlights dramatic growth, the latter encourages a more measured perspective on relativistic effects.

5 The graph of the Lorentz factor and its reciprocal

When texts present γ as a function of relative velocity β , i.e., $\gamma(\beta)$. This is often accompanied by the narrative that relativistic effects are negligible at low speeds, remain modest up to $0.5c$, and then increase without bound as the speed approaches c .

A closer look reveals that γ graphs are consistently distorted, with the horizontal axis (representing β) stretched relative to the vertical axis (representing γ).

Since both β and γ are unitless, their axes should share the same scale for an undistorted representation of their relationship. However, in all surveyed texts, the β -axis ranges from 0 to 1, while the γ -axis often extends to 10, 25, or more.

Figure 1: Comparison of $\gamma(\beta)$ graphs: the left graph uses arbitrary axis scaling, while the right graph maintains identical scales for the x -axis (β) and y -axis (γ).

If plotted with equal axis scaling, this would result in a tall and narrow graph. To avoid this, the β -axis is stretched, making the diagram wider, or equivalently, the γ -axis is compressed, making the graph appear flatter. This alteration may serve two purposes: First, it allows the graph to fit more conveniently on a page, avoiding an excessively tall diagram. Second, it visually reinforces the idea that everyday speeds are "non-relativistic," aligning with the common narrative that relativistic effects can be ignored for small β .

If both axes shared the same scale, the γ graph would be narrower, preserving the true contrast between low and high speeds without artificially flattening the low-speed region.

The distortion is even more problematic for the graph of $\epsilon(\beta) = \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$. When plotted with equal axis scales, ϵ naturally forms a quarter-, respectively a half-circle, revealing its intrinsic geometric significance. However, uneven axis scaling obscures the function's true nature, weakening its connection to an underlying geometric structure. This can be observed in the survey of textbooks, where none of the books mentions this geometric property of the curve, respectively of its underlying function. When properly scaled,

Figure 2: Image from Wikipedia: Undistorted graph of ϵ ; Original caption: α (Lorentz factor inverse) as a function of velocity—a circular arc.

the graph of ϵ naturally conveys its role as a fundamental relativistic scaling factor.

However, even sources that explicitly mention the circularity of the graph (see Figure 2), fail to draw a meaningful conclusion from its geometric property.

With the issue of distortion addressed, we now compare the graphs of $\gamma(\beta)$ and $\epsilon(\beta)$.

A key difference between the graphs of $\gamma(\beta)$ and $\epsilon(\beta)$ stems from their co-domain. While the graph of $\epsilon(\beta)$ shows all possible values, any depiction of $\gamma(\beta)$ can only display a limited range. Extending the displayed range of $\gamma(\beta)$ contributes little to additional insight. A second point is that the slope of $\gamma(\beta)$ at high velocities makes it difficult to distinguish where a vertical line intersects with the curve. Figure 3 illustrates this readability issue: At $\beta = 0.99$, the intersection of the vertical reference line with $\gamma(\beta)$ is no longer visible. At the same scale, this intersection remains visible for $\epsilon(\beta)$.

To be fair, the above point is in some way irrelevant: The graph of $\gamma(\beta)$ is always a plot based on calculated values and interpolated curves. Any value for γ that is read off such a graph has either been explicitly calculated or interpolated.

Figure 3: Comparison of the graphs of γ and ϵ , with details highlighted for $\beta = 0.99$.

The graph does not belong to any class of geometrically constructible curves. It is not a parabola, as its domain is restricted to $[-1, 1]$, unlike standard parabolic curves. Moreover, it is not a hyperbola because its asymptotes are parallel and never intersect.

The function $\epsilon(\beta)$ on the other hand forms a perfect semicircle when both axes have the same scale. As has been pointed out above, that the graph of $\epsilon(\beta)$ is a semicircle can be deduced from its equation. It can be rearranged into what is basically the equation for the unit circle:

$$\epsilon(\beta) = \sqrt{1 - \beta^2} \Rightarrow 1 = \epsilon(\beta)^2 + \beta^2 \quad (13)$$

This geometric property makes it possible to construct the graph without the need to calculate individual values. This allows students to explore relativistic effects with a compass and ruler, making abstract concepts more tangible.

The goal must not be to replace calculations with drawings. However, using a compass and a marked ruler provides an alternative approach for students who struggle with algebra and arithmetic, helping them connect calculations to a tangible experience. Even for students comfortable with algebra and arithmetic, this approach helps root their intuition in an embodied experience [LN00].

For an example of how ϵ can be determined from a graph drawn with a compass, see Figure 4.

6 The reciprocal Lorentz factor as the geometric mean

As shown in section 3, ϵ is the geometric mean of $(1 + \beta)$ and $(1 - \beta)$. This relationship is significant because the distances $(1 + \beta)$ and $(1 - \beta)$ naturally appear in a Minkowski diagram.

Figure 4: Determining ϵ with a compass and a marked ruler for $\beta = 0.8$. Scale: $5\text{cm} = 1 \Rightarrow 3\text{cm} = 0.6$

Consider a 1+1 Minkowski diagram with an event at the origin $(0, 0, 0, 0)$, its future light cone and a world line passing through the origin with speed $-1 < \beta < 1$. Then, add a horizontal line at a distance of 1 from the origin.

This horizontal line intersects the left leg of the light cone at point $A = (1, -1, 0, 0)$, the world line at point $B = (1, \beta, 0, 0)$, and the right leg of the light cone at point $C = (1, 1, 0, 0)$. The line segments $\overline{AB} = 1 + \beta$ and $\overline{BC} = 1 - \beta$ can be measured, and their lengths multiplied. The resulting product represents both ϵ^2 and the spacetime interval S^2 between the points $(0, 0, 0, 0)$ and $(1, \beta, 0, 0)$.

By drawing a horizontal line at a distance t from the x-axis, the spacetime interval between $(0, 0, 0, 0)$ and any event $(t, t\beta, 0, 0)$ can be determined. See Figure 5.

This relationship between an event and the light cone of another event is absent from the surveyed textbooks. The next section will explore this

Figure 5: Determining the distances $1 + \beta$ and $1 - \beta$, respectively $t + t\beta$ and $t - t\beta$, from a Minkowski diagram.

relationship further.

The spacetime interval as the power of a point

The relationship highlighted in the previous section is insightful on its own. However, it would be even more useful if ϵ or s could be measured directly from the Minkowski diagram. Achieving this requires incorporating either a semicircle or a full circle into the diagram.

One possibility is to add a circle into the 1 + 1-Minkowski diagram. Construct a circle centered at $(t, 0, 0, 0)$ with radius t . Next, draw a vertical line through $(t, t\beta, 0, 0)$, parallel to the t -axis. The distance from $(t, t\beta, 0, 0)$ to the intersection of the vertical line and the circle represents the square root of the spacetime interval between $(0, 0, 0, 0)$ and $(t, \beta t, 0, 0)$.

In a 1 + 2-Minkowski diagram, circles arise naturally. Given an event E at $(t_E, x_E, y_E, 0)$, consider a plane parallel to the xy -plane at a distance t_E from the origin. This plane intersects the future light cone of $(0, 0, 0, 0)$, forming a circle c . Any event with coordinates $(t_E, x, y, 0)$ lies within this plane.

While Herman Minkowski could visualize light cones as three-dimensional objects, he lacked the means to draw a spacetime diagram that could be

Figure 6: Power of a point as pictured on Wikipedia.org By Ag2gaeh - Own work, CC BY-SA 4.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=107079127>

rotated and viewed from all angles. However, modern software such as GeoGebra or Desmos allows students to easily create 3D Minkowski diagrams. These diagrams provide a clear visualization of the geometric relationship between two events.

Once students have created such a diagram, they can view it from above. From this perspective, they see a circle (the conic section between the plane and the light cone) and a point (the event E on the plane). This is the key moment for students to make the final connection: The spacetime interval is encoded in the geometric relationship between the circle and the point. This is a connection students can discover on their own.

The relationship between the event's representative point and the circle formed by the intersection of the light cone and the plane is known as the *power of the point with respect to the circle*.¹

The power of a point, is a fundamental geometric concept introduced by

¹I owe the insight that the spacetime interval is related to the power of a point to a video by Norman Wildberger [Wil14]. While he did not explicitly make this connection, his geometric analysis provided the foundation for this insight.

Swiss mathematician Jacob Steiner in 1826 [Ste26]. A full exploration of the geometric meaning of *the power of a point* is beyond the scope of this paper. If students are unfamiliar with this concept, it should be briefly introduced.

For a point P and a circle c centered at O with radius r Figure 6, the power $\Pi(P)$ is given by:

$$\Pi(P) = |OP|^2 - r^2 \quad (14)$$

Just as the spacetime interval distinguishes between timelike, lightlike, and spacelike separations, the power of a point distinguishes whether a point lies inside, on, or outside a circle:

- If P is *inside* the circle, then $\Pi < 0$.
- If P is *on* the circle, then $\Pi = 0$.
- If P is *outside* the circle, then $\Pi > 0$.

The connection between the power of a point and the spacetime interval is straightforward:

- If an event $E = (t, x, y, 0)$ is timelike related to $O = (0, 0, 0, 0)$, it lies inside the light cone. Consequently, the representative point of E will lie inside the circle.
- If an event $E = (t, x, y, 0)$ is lightlike related to $O = (0, 0, 0, 0)$, it lies on the light cone. Consequently, the representative point of E will lie on the circle.
- If an event $E = (t, x, y, 0)$ is spacelike related to $O = (0, 0, 0, 0)$, it lies outside the light cone. Consequently, the representative point of E will lie outside the circle.

Figure 7: Light cones with a timelike and a spacelike related event. Left: the spacetime interval as $1/2$ the shortest chord for timelike intervals. Right: a tangent line segment for spacelike intervals.

So far, we have only applied the geometric approach to determine ϵ or the proper time for timelike intervals. However, this approach also applies to spacelike intervals.

In a $2 + 1$ -Minkowski diagram, the square root of the spacetime interval is given by $s = \sqrt{\Pi}$. For events inside the circle c , s corresponds to half the shortest chord passing through the point representing event E . For events outside the circle c , $\sqrt{\Pi}$ is the tangential distance between E and c (see Figure 7).

Interpreting the spacetime interval through the power of a point provides Minkowski diagrams with a new perspective—one that has remained unexplored since their inception.

Beyond visualizing the quantitative relationship (i.e., the spacetime interval) between two events, examining the conic section offers another advantage. This is particularly relevant in a $1 + 1$ Minkowski diagram, where it may not be immediately clear what it means for an event to be inside, on, or outside the light cone. Students might perceive the event's representative point as merely above, below, left, or right of the light signal's path. However, incorporating a circle makes the distinction between inside, on, or

outside the boundary more intuitive.

7 Conclusion

Generations of students have learned special relativity using the Lorentz factor and have built their intuition around it. Hardly any popular presentation of the theory omits it. Finally, the intellectual feat of Hendrik Lorentz, after whom the factor is named, cannot be overstated.

Nevertheless, this paper has demonstrated that γ is not the most straightforward approach to relativistic effects. The very idea of calculating the reciprocal of a number between 0 and 1 only to divide another quantity (e.g., length or time) by this reciprocal highlights the redundancy and computational inefficiency of using γ .

In contrast, the direct multiplicative relationship of ϵ with length contraction and time dilation fosters a clearer intuition in students. As they move on to more challenging topics, both conceptually and mathematically, they can build on this solid foundation.

However, the most significant boost to students' intuition comes from relating ϵ to the circle. Being able to draw its graph with utmost precision—without making a single calculation or interpolation—gives students a firm grasp of how ϵ relates to β . Even if they do not recall specific values of ϵ for particular speeds, the relationship itself is easy to remember.

Teachers and lecturers seeking new didactic tools may appreciate the geometric approach. They have the opportunity to let their students *develop* an alternative perspective that is absent from the standard literature.

The geometric approach takes advantage of modern students' access to 3D visualization tools. It is time to step beyond paper and 1+1 Minkowski diagrams.

A deliberate push to replace γ with ϵ might be seen as overly ambitious or insistent. This is akin to discussions about replacing π with τ . Therefore,

rather than pushing for an immediate overhaul of textbooks, it is more constructive to explore if and how ϵ can actually improve the teaching of special relativity.

Future research should assess whether ϵ offers a more effective approach to teaching special relativity than the traditional use of γ . By focusing on its geometric interpretation and intuitive construction with basic tools, ϵ may provide clearer insights into relativistic effects. Empirical studies in physics education could evaluate whether this perspective enhances conceptual understanding and reduces common misconceptions.

A Set of Sample Problems

The following section presents some sample problems for the kinematics of special relativity. The solutions presented do not strictly adhere to constructions using only a collapsible compass and straightedge. Instead, the solutions make use of fixed compasses, marked rulers, set squares, or software such as GeoGebra. They are intended to be easily accessible to students.

These scenarios involve only clocks and focus on events where clocks coincide. They avoid abstract coordinate systems but also human observers such as Alice and Bob, as well as common vehicles like trains, planes, and rocket ships. However, these examples can easily be expanded with the usual narratives.

All examples use natural units, where $c = 1$, and distance and time are expressed in the same unit.

A.1 Determining the Proper Time

A.1.1 Problem

This problem is a classic special relativity question: How much time elapses on a moving clock between two events, as measured in a given frame of

reference?

In this example, a single clock A is present at both events, while two other clocks, B and C , remain stationary relative to each other. The first event is the coincidence of the clocks A and B . The second event is the coincidence of the clocks A and C . B and C are synchronized according to Einstein's synchronization convention. The question is: How does the elapsed time on clock A compare to the difference between the two clock readings at B and C ?

A.1.2 Solution

1. Draw a line segment a with endpoints labeled AB and AC .
 - These points mark where clock A coincides with clocks B and C , respectively.
 - The segment a represents the trajectory of clock A as it moves between clocks B and C .
2. Draw a circle centered at AB .
 - The radius must exceed the distance between AB and AC .
 - This radius represents the difference in clock readings between clocks B and C , i.e., Δt .
3. Draw a line segment τ_A starting at AC and perpendicular to segment a .
 - The segment τ_A extends from AC to the circle's circumference.
 - **The length of τ_A represents the proper time elapsed on clock A .**

A.2 Determining the Coordinate Time

A.2.1 Problem

This problem is the inverse of the previous one: Instead of determining the proper time elapsed on clock A , we now seek to determine the coordinate time interval between events.

As before, we consider three clocks: A , B , and C . However, this time, the proper time τ_A elapsed on clock A is given. We now seek to determine the time displayed on clock C at the moment it coincides with A .

A.2.2 Solution

1. Draw a line segment a with endpoints labeled AB and AC .
2. Draw the segment τ_A starting at AC , perpendicular to a .
 - The length of this segment represents the proper time τ_A elapsed on clock A as it moves from B to C .
3. Draw a circle centered at AB such that the free end of τ_A lies on its circumference.
 - **The radius of the circle represents Δt , the coordinate time interval derived from the readings of clocks B and C .**
 - This is also the time displayed on clock C if the coordinate time of event AB is set to zero.

A.3 Determining the Traveled Distance Based on Clock Readings

A.3.1 Problem

As before, we consider three clocks: A , B , and C . However, this time, we are given the proper time elapsed on A , $\Delta\tau$, and the time difference between the

readings of clocks B and C , Δt . We must determine the spatial coordinate separation between B and C .

A.3.2 Solution

1. Draw a line f , representing the trajectory of clock A , and mark the point AB on this line.
2. Draw a parallel line g at a distance corresponding to the proper time $\Delta\tau$ elapsed on A .
3. Draw a circle centered at AB .
 - The circle's radius must be greater than the distance between f and g , ensuring it fully encloses the gap.
 - This radius represents the time difference between the readings of clocks B and C , i.e., Δt .
4. Identify the intersections of the circle with line g .
 - The circle intersects line g at two points.
 - Draw a line through one of these intersection points, perpendicular to both f and g .
 - This new line intersects f at a single point, which we label AC .
 - **The distance between AB and AC represents the proper distance between clocks B and C .**

A.4 Modelling the no-twins-no-paradox scenario (aka the twin paradox)

A.4.1 Problem

This problem is a reprise of the proper time problem. It is a stripped-down version of the popular twin paradox. Again, we have three clocks A , B , and

C. However, this time all three clocks move inertially relative to each other. Their relative motion is such that *A* and *B* meet at an event *AB*, then *B* and *C* meet at a second event *BC*, and finally, *A* and *C* meet at a third event *AC*.

The question is how much proper time $\Delta\tau_A$ elapses on *A* between the events *AB* and *AC* compared to the combined proper time that elapses on *B* between *AB* and *BC* and on *C* between *BC* and *AC*, i.e.,

$$\Delta\tau_A \quad \text{vs.} \quad \Delta\tau_B + \Delta\tau_C.$$

A.4.2 Solution

1. Draw a triangle and label its vertices *AB*, *AC*, and *BC*. - The line segment between *AB* and *AC* is labeled *a*. - The segment between *AB* and *BC* is labeled *b*. - The segment between *BC* and *AC* is labeled *c*.

2. Construct a line segment $\Delta\tau_B$ starting at *BC* and perpendicular to *b*. - This segment represents the proper time that elapses on *B* between *AB* and *BC*. - Draw a circle centered at *AB* that passes through the free end of $\Delta\tau_B$. - The radius of this circle represents the temporal separation between *AB* and *BC*, i.e., $\Delta T(AB, BC)$.

3. Similarly, construct a line segment $\Delta\tau_C$ starting at *AC* and perpendicular to *c*. - This segment represents the proper time that elapses on *C* between *BC* and *AC*. - Draw a circle centered at *BC* that passes through the free end of $\Delta\tau_C$. - The radius of this circle represents the temporal separation between *BC* and *AC*, i.e., $\Delta T(BC, AC)$.

4. Construct a larger circle centered at *AB* with a radius equal to the sum of the two previous radii:

$$\Delta T(AB, BC) + \Delta T(BC, AC).$$

- This radius represents the total temporal separation between *AB* and *AC*.

5. Finally, draw a line segment starting at BC and perpendicular to a . - Extend this segment until it reaches the larger circle around AB . - **The length of this segment represents the proper time $\Delta\tau_A$ that elapses on A between AB and AC .**

A check of the three line segments $\Delta\tau_A$, $\Delta\tau_B$ and $\Delta\tau_C$ will show: $\Delta\tau_A > \Delta\tau_B + \Delta\tau_C$.

B Survey of Textbooks on the Lorentz Factor

This annex surveys how different textbooks introduce the Lorentz factor γ , whether they mention its reciprocal ϵ , and how they use graphs to illustrate relativistic effects.

This survey does not aim to evaluate the overall didactic merits of these books. The primary goal is to determine whether the approach presented in this paper appears in any existing textbook. However, since this survey is not exhaustive, there may be other books that already use this approach. If such books or papers exist, any references to previous presentations of this approach would be appreciated.

The books can be grouped into four categories:

1. Books that introduce γ solely as an algebraic shorthand for $1/\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$. These books neither introduce the term "Lorentz factor" nor assign any other name to γ , nor do they discuss its historical, physical, or algebraic significance.
2. Books that introduce γ by name, either as the Lorentz factor or with an alternative descriptive term.
3. Books that analyze γ in greater detail. These books, for example, explore γ as a function of speed and analyze its behavior as $\beta \rightarrow 1$.
4. Books that do not introduce γ at all, instead consistently using $1/\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$ or $\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$ where appropriate.

B.1 Books that introduce γ as shorthand

In the survey, the following books introduce γ purely as a shorthand for $1/\sqrt{1-\beta^2}$:

- *Spacetime and Geometry: An Introduction to General Relativity* (S. Carroll, 2019)
- *Relativity: A Journey Through Warped Space and Time* (D. Mayerson, C. Charles, and J. Golec, 2019)
- *Spezielle Relativitätstheorie: Eine Einführung Mithilfe des K-Kalküls* (R. Kremer, 2023)
- *Solved Problems and Systematic Introduction to Special Relativity* (M. Tsamparlis, 2024)

These books introduce γ without discussing its conceptual significance or its role beyond algebraic convenience. They neither justify its use nor explore its inverse ϵ as an alternative. As a result, students using these texts may easily overlook γ .

B.2 Books that introduce γ by name

The second category of books introduces γ by referring to it as the "Lorentz factor" or "so-called Lorentz factor." These books are:

- *A First Course on Symmetry, Special Relativity and Quantum Mechanics: The Foundations of Physics* (G. Kunstatter and A. Das, 2020)
- *Modern Special Relativity: A Student's Guide with Discussions and Examples* (J. Rafelski, 2022)

Assigning a name to γ allows students to recognize it in books, discussions, or lectures where neither the symbol nor the explicit formula is stated.

This makes it easier to reference and recall, reinforcing its role as a key quantity in relativity. However, naming it does not necessarily provide students with deeper insight into its meaning or its connection to relativistic effects.

B.3 Books that discuss γ in detail

The third category includes books that delve a little deeper into how γ can be used to develop an intuition for how relativistic effects depend on relative speed.

In the following section, I provide a brief overview of how these books present γ .

B.3.1 *Introduction to Special Relativity* (R. Resnick, 1968)

This book is unusual in that it performs all calculations without ever using γ in any formula. However, in Section 2.3, Resnick introduces γ only to examine its values, along with those of ϵ (though he does not name it explicitly, instead writing out its formula) for different values of β . He does not explain why he introduces the symbol γ at that point, nor does he mention that it is often referred to as the Lorentz factor.

The book also includes graphs for both γ and ϵ in two separate diagrams. Both have distorted axes. The axis for β has the same scale in both diagrams. The axes for ϵ and γ have different scales. With the choice of relative position, this gives the impression, that the two graphs have a symmetry which in fact does not exist. The choice of the scales might explain why Resnick did not recognize the geometric property of the ϵ -graph.

B.3.2 *Spacetime Physics: Introduction to Special Relativity* (E. F. Taylor and J. A. Wheeler, 1992)

This book introduces γ with the following statement:

Fig. 2-3. (a) A plot of $\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$ as a function of β (b) A plot of $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$ as a function of β

Figure 8: Graphs for ϵ and γ from *Introduction to Special Relativity*

”The awkward expression $1/(1 - v^2/c^2)^{1/2}$ occurs often in what follows. For simplicity, this expression is given the symbol Greek lower-case γ .”

They note that it would be better to use γ_{rel} to indicate that the value of γ depends on the relative speed between two frames of reference.

However, instead of referring to γ as the Lorentz factor, Taylor and Wheeler introduce their own terminology, calling it the ”time-stretch factor.” In the subsection where they discuss the time-stretch factor, they state:

”Finally, the stretch factor is often used as an alternative measure of particle speed: A particle moves with a speed such that the stretch factor is 10.”

Unlike Resnick’s text, this book does not provide any graphs.

B.3.3 Relativity: Special, General, and Cosmological (Rindler, 2006)

[Rin06]

Among the books that discuss γ , this book takes a straight forward approach. It introduces γ as ”the famous Lorentz factor” and includes a conventional (i.e., distorted) graph of γ . In addition, Rindler notes:

”Note its slow initial increase and its asymptote at $v = c$; $v \geq c$ leads to unphysical transformations, a first hint of the relativistic speed limit.”

B.3.4 The Special Theory of Relativity: A Mathematical Approach. Second Edition (Rahaman, 2022)

This book is unique in that it does not introduce γ as a symbol, nor does it name the Lorentz factor or any equivalent term. However, it includes two graphs that appear to represent $\epsilon(\beta)$ and $\gamma(\beta)$, respectively.

Figure 9: Graph of γ similar to Figure 2.5 in Rindler with distorted axes

The graph of $\epsilon(\beta)$ is particularly notable because it is undistorted, correctly displaying the expected quarter-circle shape. However, despite this geometric property being clearly visible, the text does not discuss its significance.

In contrast, the graph of $\gamma(\beta)$ is distorted and, additionally, has an unusual choice of axis placement: the intersection of the x-axis and y-axis is set to $(0, 1)$. If examined quickly or without careful attention, this could create the misleading impression that the graph starts at the point $(0, 0)$, which is incorrect since $\gamma(0) = 1$, not 0.

Similar to [Res68] the choice of the scales and the relative position of the two graphs suggests a symmetry that is not present in the functions: The distorted graph of $\gamma(\beta)$ appears visually similar to the graph of β rotated by 90° the graphs can be found in figure 4.2 on page 41 of the book.. Even if this effect was not intentional, it is misleading because it suggests a direct geometric similarity between $\epsilon(\beta)$ and $\gamma(\beta)$ that does not exist. Since the

graph of $\gamma(\beta)$ already has counterintuitive properties, presenting it in a way that visually mimics another function only adds to possible confusion.

B.3.5 Special relativity for the enthusiast (Strohm, 2023)

This book introduces γ as the γ -factor. In a distorted diagram it shows both $\epsilon(\beta)$ and $\gamma(\beta)$ Figure 10. The graph is a good example how the geometric property of $\gamma(\beta)$ is hidden by the choice of scales for the axes. By placing both graphs in the same diagram, the diagram does not imply a symmetry as [Res68] and [Rah22] It discusses briefly the relevance of the three notations $\gamma(v)$, γ_v and γ and how the curve behaves in different ranges.

B.4 Books that Don't Introduce γ at All

In the survey, several books explain special relativity without introducing γ as a symbol or referring to it by name. This demonstrates that the Lorentz factor is not a necessary component of relativistic formulations.

- *The Geometry of Spacetime: An Introduction to Special and General Relativity* (Callahan, 2000)
- *The Geometry of Spacetime: A Mathematical Introduction to Relativity Theory* (Oloff, 2023)
- *A Mathematical Journey to Relativity: Deriving Special and General Relativity with Basic Mathematics* (Boskoff and Capozziello, 2024)
- *Special Relativity: For Inquiring Minds. Undergraduate Lecture Notes in Physics* (Deshko, 2022)

The fact that these authors successfully convey relativistic concepts without γ supports the conclusion of this paper: while γ is commonly used, it is not indispensable. Alternative approaches, such as those based on ϵ , may provide clearer conceptual insights.

Figure 10: Graph similar to Figure 8.3 found in [Str23], with ϵ and γ in one diagram with equal but distorted graphs, the geometric property of the graph of ϵ is not obvious

B.5 Conclusion of the Survey

The survey of textbooks on special relativity reveals that the introduction and use of γ primarily serve as a mathematical and notational convenience rather than a pedagogical tool. Although γ is widely adopted due to its historical significance and prevalence in the literature, its educational value often remains limited to algebraic simplifications rather than conceptual clarity.

The graphical presentations of $\gamma(\beta)$ frequently distort the relationship between relative velocity and relativistic effects, potentially reinforcing misconceptions about the nature of relativistic scaling. Moreover, alternative approaches that emphasize ϵ directly are largely absent from the surveyed texts, despite their potential to offer a more intuitive understanding of relativistic effects.

C Analyzing the geometric identity

The geometric identity, which is cited several times in this paper

$$1 = \epsilon^2 + \beta^2 \tag{15}$$

is central to understanding the relation between relative speed and relativistic effects. However, it becomes an algebraic tautology once ϵ is replaced by its explicit formulation $\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}$:

$$1 = \sqrt{1 - \beta^2}^2 + \beta^2 \Rightarrow 1 = (1 - \beta^2) + \beta^2 \tag{16}$$

This may leave the attentive reader or student with a feeling that the geometric approach is pretending to be fundamental while it is hiding a self-referential tautology. To regain the feeling of fundamental physical insight, we can reformulate the above equation. To do so, we will use the formulas for length contraction

$$l = \epsilon \cdot l_0 \tag{17}$$

and time dilation

$$\Delta\tau = \epsilon \cdot \Delta t \tag{18}$$

From these two formulas and the definition of ϵ we can obtain the following three equations:

$$\epsilon = \sqrt{1 - \beta^2} \tag{19}$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{l}{l_0} \tag{20}$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{\Delta\tau}{\Delta t} \tag{21}$$

We now replace each ϵ in the following equation with one of the above explicit expressions

$$\epsilon^2 = \epsilon \cdot \epsilon \tag{22}$$

So we obtain the equation

$$\sqrt{1 - \beta^2}^2 = \frac{l}{l_0} \cdot \frac{\Delta\tau}{\Delta t} \tag{23}$$

which can be transformed into

$$1 = \frac{l}{l_0} \cdot \frac{\Delta\tau}{\Delta t} + \beta^2 \tag{24}$$

Although this identity no longer mirrors the Pythagorean form as directly as equation (15), it combines three observable quantities into a single expression: the ratio of measured to proper length, the ratio of proper to coordinate time, and the square of relative speed. It captures a *relativistic trade-off*: the faster an object moves, the more of the total “budget” is consumed by the β^2 term, leaving less for the agreement between proper and coordinate

quantities. A high relative speed forces a reduction in measured length and slows the passage of proper time. Far from being a tautology in disguise, the identity reflects a physical constraint that governs how relativistic effects scale with motion.

Declarations

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

Data Availability

No new data were generated or analyzed in this study. All necessary information is provided within the manuscript.

Ethics Statement

This study does not involve human participants, human data, or animals, and therefore does not require ethical approval.

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